

Neural BRDF Decomposition for Consistent Material Recovery in Inverse Rendering - Supplementary Material

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1 METHOD

1.1 BRDF Form

We use the Cook-Torrance micro-facet BRDF (Cook and Torrance, 1982). F is the Fresnel term given by

$$F = F_0 + (1 - F_0)(1 - (\omega_o \cdot \mathbf{h}))^5 \quad (1)$$

where $F_0 = \rho_m \rho_a + 0.04(1 - \rho_m)$ is the basic reflection ratio and \mathbf{h} is the half angle between ω_i and ω_o .

G is the Geometric attenuation term given by:

$$G(\mathbf{n}, \omega_i, \omega_o, k) = \frac{(\omega_i \cdot \mathbf{n})(\omega_o \cdot \mathbf{n})}{((\omega_i \cdot \mathbf{n})(1 - k) + k)((\omega_o \cdot \mathbf{n})(1 - k) + k)} \quad (2)$$

where $k = \rho_r^4/2$ And D is the distribution of the micro-facet normals which is given as follows.

$$D(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{h}, \rho_r) = \frac{\rho_r^4}{\pi((\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{h})(\rho_r^4 - 1) + 1)^2} \quad (3)$$

1.2 Losses and Regularization in Inverse Rendering

During inverse rendering, in addition to the rendering loss, We impose two regularization terms on the final inverse rendering loss (Hasselgren et al., 2022; Munkberg et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2023). One is a term to enforce smoothness ℓ_{smooth}

$$\ell_{\text{smooth}} = \|\rho_{\text{material}}(\mathbf{p}) - \rho_{\text{material}}(\mathbf{p} + \epsilon)\|_2, \quad (4)$$

where ϵ is set to be 5×10^{-3} and \mathbf{p} is a point on the surface. This ℓ_{smooth} encourages the predicted materials (roughness, metallic, and albedo) to be smooth in the space. The other regularization term ℓ_{light} is imposed to encourage the diffuse part of the PT lighting $L_d = \frac{1}{N_d} \sum_i L_{pt}(\omega_i)$ to be closer to neutral white lighting. This is done by computing the mean of RGB values of the diffuse light and minimizing the difference between the RGB values and their mean,

$$\ell_{\text{light}} = \sum_c ([L_d]_c - \frac{1}{3} \sum_c [L_d]_c), \quad (5)$$

where c is the index of RGB channel of L_d .

The final loss for the inverse rendering stage is

$$\ell = \ell_{\text{render}} + \lambda_{\text{smooth}} \ell_{\text{smooth}} + \lambda_{\text{light}} \ell_{\text{light}} \quad (6)$$

where λ_{smooth} and λ_{light} are two predefined scalars.

1.3 Training Details

For Stage 1 of our pipeline (Neural Decomposition), both RF and AO network pairs are trained on 2^{14} samples. We use Adam optimizer (Kingma and Ba, 2015) ($\beta_1 = 0.9$, $\beta_2 = 0.999$) with a learning rate of $3e^{-5}$.

During Stage 3 (Inverse Rendering), similar to NeRO (Liu et al., 2023), for our path tracing component, we sample $N_d = 512$ rays on the diffuse lobe and $N_s = 256$ rays on the specular lobe. As in our Neural Decomposition stage, we use the Adam optimizer (Kingma and Ba, 2015) with $\beta_1 = 0.9$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$. Similarly to NeRO (Liu et al., 2023), we impose a warm-up learning rate schedule with the learning rate increasing from $1e^{-5}$ to $5e^{-4}$ in 1k steps and decreasing to $1e^{-5}$ in the remainder of the total of 100k steps.

2 DATASETS

2.1 Glossy-Synthetic Dataset

The objects in the Glossy-Synthetic dataset (Liu et al., 2023) are shown in Figure 1.

2.2 DTU Dataset

Each scan of the DTU dataset (Jensen et al., 2014) contains 49 or 64 multi-view images of a stationary scene lit under 7 lighting conditions. We select 8 scans: **scan55**, **scan65**, **scan69**, **scan106**, **scan110**, **scan114**, **scan118**, **scan122** for our evaluations. These scans in particular have corresponding rotated scans also available in the dataset (although we do not make use of the rotated scans). These objects can be seen in Figure 2

Figure 1: Multiview images of objects from the Glossy-Synthetic Dataset. The object in the top row (L-R) are Angel, Bell, Cat and Horse. Objects in the bottom row (L-R) are Luyu, Potion, TBell and Teapot

Figure 2: Objects from the DTU dataset (Jensen et al., 2014). The object in the top row (L-R) are scan55, scan65, scan69, scan106. Objects in the bottom row (L-R) are scan110, scan114, scan118, scan122

2.3 Our Datasets

For the Multilit-Real dataset we capture 47 views for the Baobab object, and 58 views for the Lemur object for 5 lighting conditions each. The dataset has a total of 515 images. We use 1 view in each lighting condition for evaluation and testing, and we use the rest of the data for training. The resolution of all the images is 3024×3024 .

For the Multilit-Synthetic dataset we have 150 views for the Einar model and the Native American model each, for each of the 5 lighting conditions, giving a total for 1500 images in total. Here also, we use 1 view in each lighting condition for testing, and the rest of the images for training. The resolution of all the images is 2048×2048 . Additionally, because we know ground truth materials for the synthetic models, we have rendered 1 view each in 3 novel lighting conditions, unseen during training. These three renders are used as the ground truth images for the evaluations shown in Figures 8 and 9.

Examples of images from Multilit-Real and Multi-Synthetic datasets are shown in Figure 3.

3 EXPERIMENTS

Each run of our inverse rendering pipeline yields materials that can be exported as per-vertex material at-

Figure 3: Top two rows show images of real objects, Lemur and Baobab, from Multilit-Real. Next two rows show images of Einar and Native American from Multilit-Synthetic.

Figure 4: Material attributes extracted from points on the Einar model are used to render the different spheres. The Einar reconstruction is with City light as our PT component.

tributes (Figure 4) or as texture maps (Figure 5) for further use in standard rendering pipelines.

3.1 Multi-Light comparisons

Here we compare renderings produced by our approach when it is used to recover materials consistent with multiple lighting conditions (Figure 6), and produce a novel render under novel lighting conditions. These have not been seen during training. Figures 7, 8 and 9 show qualitative comparisons for this evaluation.

3.2 DTU Holdout Comparisons

We evaluate material consistency on the DTU dataset (Jensen et al., 2014). We use first 6 of the 7

Figure 5: Albedo (left), Metalness (Center), Roughness (Right) maps recovered for the real object Baobab from images captured under multiple lighting conditions - with White light as the PT component.

lighting conditions, split into 3 sets of 2 lighting conditions each. We run NeRO (Liu et al., 2023) on each set, using only 1 lighting condition per set, yielding 3 SVBRDFs. Our method also runs on each set, using the lighting condition NeRO used as the PT component and both as SH components, also recovering 3 SVBRDFs. Figures 10 and 11 show our method achieves lower material variance (visualized in the image space of a novel view). Both NeRO (Liu et al., 2023) and our approach use the remaining 1 common lighting condition for geometry recovery.

3.3 Single Lighting Comparisons

Novel view renderings for the complete set of Glossy-Synthetic (Liu et al., 2023) objects are shown in Figure 12. The complete set of quantitative results based on the metrics of PSNR, SSIM (Wang et al., 2004) and LPIPS (Zhang et al., 2018) is shown in Table 1.

These results show that our method works well for single lighting conditions as well.

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Figure 6: Average of variance in material parameters recovered by NeRO (Liu et al., 2023) and our approach for synthetic objects Einar and Native American from Multilit-Synth dataset shown in the novel view image space.

Figure 7: Novel rendering comparisons for Einar and Native American models, captured under different lighting configurations and rendered under novel lighting condition 1. Ground truth image is on left of the top row, followed by NeRO's renderings (remaining top row) and our renderings in the bottom row. The lighting condition environment map is shown in the inset.

Figure 8: Novel rendering comparisons for Einar and Native American models, captured under different lighting configurations and rendered under novel lighting condition 2. Ground truth image is on left of the top row, followed by NeRO's renderings (remaining top row) and our renderings are in the bottom row. The lighting condition environment map is shown in the inset.

Figure 9: Novel rendering comparisons for Einar and Native American models, captured under different lighting configurations and rendered under novel lighting condition 3. Ground truth image is on left of the top row, followed by NeRO's renderings (remaining top row) and our renderings are in the bottom row. The lighting condition environment map is shown in the inset.

Figure 10: Average of variance in material parameters recovered by NeRO (Liu et al., 2023) and our approach for objects scan55, scan65, scan69, scan106 (L-R) from the DTU dataset shown in the novel view image space with GT novel view, variance map for NeRO (Liu et al., 2023) and the variance map for our approach (Top-Bottom).

Figure 11: Average of variance in material parameters recovered by NeRO (Liu et al., 2023) and our approach for objects scan110, scan114, scan118, scan122 (L-R) from the DTU dataset shown in the novel view image space with GT novel view, variance map for NeRO (Liu et al., 2023) and the variance map for our approach (Top-Bottom).

Figure 12: Novel View Rendering Comparisons under Single Environment Lighting on the complete Glossy-Synthetic dataset

Table 1: **Quantitative Results on Novel Views of the Glossy-Synthetic Dataset.** We compare our method with Lu-GS (Cui et al., 2025) NeILF++ (Zhang et al., 2023), GS (Jiang et al., 2024) and NeRO (Liu et al., 2023). *GS figures have been obtained from the results published in their supplementary material since the complete code wasn't available. **Bold** means the best performance while underline means the second best.

	Angel	Bell	Cat	Horse	Luyu	Potion	TBell	Teapot	Average
	PSNR \uparrow								
Lu-GS	19.82	19.87	24.37	22.53	21.01	25.70	16.14	18.09	20.94
NeILF++	24.29	25.28	26.07	24.63	24.34	26.60	23.88	21.52	24.58
GS	28.07	28.08	31.81	25.53	27.25	30.08	24.48	23.57	27.36
NeRO	28.18	<u>31.25</u>	<u>31.02</u>	<u>26.26</u>	<u>28.02</u>	<u>32.81</u>	<u>28.08</u>	27.43	<u>29.13</u>
Ours	28.18	31.69	31.33	26.31	28.13	33.49	28.36	<u>27.37</u>	29.36
	SSIM \uparrow								
Lu-GS	0.868	0.854	0.899	0.874	0.851	0.921	0.794	0.824	0.861
NeILF++	0.883	0.877	0.902	0.862	0.893	0.891	0.885	0.857	0.881
GS	0.923	0.920	0.961	0.918	0.915	0.936	0.897	0.899	0.921
NeRO	0.941	<u>0.947</u>	<u>0.967</u>	<u>0.902</u>	0.944	<u>0.959</u>	<u>0.939</u>	0.950	0.944
Ours	0.941	0.948	0.968	<u>0.902</u>	0.944	0.963	0.940	<u>0.949</u>	0.944
	LPIPS \downarrow								
Lu-GS	0.0580	0.0963	0.0569	0.0618	0.0812	0.0597	0.1191	0.0933	0.0783
NeILF++	0.1161	0.1454	0.1321	0.1229	0.0988	0.1593	0.1612	0.1260	0.1327
GS	0.0650	0.0970	0.0560	0.0620	0.0640	0.0870	0.1210	0.0900	0.0803
NeRO	0.0448	<u>0.0504</u>	<u>0.0347</u>	0.0679	0.0463	<u>0.0505</u>	0.0642	<u>0.0484</u>	<u>0.0509</u>
Ours	0.0448	0.0500	0.0342	<u>0.0675</u>	<u>0.0467</u>	0.0476	0.0642	0.0483	0.0504